

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF WORKS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF JANE EYRE)

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Abstract

This article highlights the didactic and methodological significance of linguistic analysis of literary works, in particular Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre", in the process of teaching a foreign language. Literary texts serve not only to master language units in language learning, but also to develop intercultural competence. The article considers methods for developing analytical thinking, language sensitivity and contextual understanding skills in students by analyzing the lexical, grammatical, stylistic and pragmatic aspects of the work. The figurative language, speech style and socio-cultural connotations of the work "Jane Eyre" are studied, and suggestions are made for its effective use in foreign language lessons. The study is aimed at ensuring the harmony of language and culture through literary texts in foreign language teaching.

Keywords: *literary work, linguistic analysis, Jane Eyre, foreign language, language teaching, stylistics, intercultural competence, language and culture.*

Introduction

Modern language teaching methodology is aimed not only at memorizing grammatical rules and increasing vocabulary, but also at a deep understanding of the use of the language being studied in a cultural context, stylistic richness and pragmatic aspects. The role of literary texts in the process of mastering a foreign language is incomparable, because they embody an example of real and figurative use of the language. From this point of view, linguistic analysis of literary works, in particular, classic novels in English, in foreign language lessons is an effective teaching method.

A literary text is a complex language material enriched with stylistic devices, figurative expressions, cultural and historical connotations, in addition to simple grammatical structures. By analyzing such texts, students penetrate deeper layers of the language, better understand how language works, what meanings and functions it performs. Especially since the language of literature expresses life events in an artistic form, it serves as a solid foundation for language learners to understand various forms of communication and freely express their thoughts.

Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" is one of the most famous classic works of English literature, and is notable not only for its artistic value, but also

for its unique language. The psychological situations expressed in the work, social relationships, interpersonal communication forms, and the preservation of ancient language elements that formed the basis for the development of modern English make this text a rich source for analysis in the process of language learning. In particular, phraseological units, stylistic devices, syntactic constructions, and pragmatic elements in the novel play an important role in deepening students' linguistic knowledge.

This article discusses how linguistic analysis of "Jane Eyre" in foreign language classes affects students' language skills, what methods can be used in the analysis process, and the advantages of such an approach. It also analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of developing students' stylistic sensitivity, developing contextual analysis skills, and increasing intercultural competence through the language of the work.

The relevance of the topic is that today there is a growing need to teach a foreign language not only on the basis of grammar, but also on the basis of real speech and cultural context. Such an approach makes the language learning process not only effective, but also interesting and close to life. Thus, it becomes possible to study a foreign language more deeply through the language of classic works such as "Jane Eyre".

Main part: The use of literary works in the practice of teaching a foreign language, especially the approach based on linguistic analysis, plays an important role in modern methodology. Because literary texts embody different layers of the language: phonetic, lexical, grammatical, stylistic and pragmatic aspects. This creates a richer and more natural language environment for students learning the language.

Through literary texts, students learn speech patterns that are close to real communication. Through this, they have the opportunity to understand contextually, understand stylistic differences, and perceive how language is used in various communicative situations. In this regard, linguistic analysis develops not only analytical thinking, but also language sensitivity and cultural thinking.

Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" is a vivid example of 19th-century English. The work contains a rich lexical layer, complex syntactic constructions, and stylistic devices with socio-cultural connotations. Through linguistic analysis of this work, students gain knowledge at several language levels.

The novel is lexically rich, with a wide use of outdated words typical of the time (thou, thee, nay, ere), poetic synonyms, and emotionally charged words.

Students observe lexical development by comparing these words with modern English.

Example: *“I am no bird; and no net ensnares me: I am a free human being with an independent will.”*

In this sentence, the word “ensnares” — “to trap” — has a strong emotional connotation, highlighting the theme of free will.

The work often features complex sentence structures, inversion, and a variety of verb tenses. By studying these grammatical structures, students gain a deeper understanding of the role of grammatical units in a real text.

For example: *“Were I in your place, I would not act thus.”*

This sentence uses the subjunctive mood, which is a form of classical conditional sentences. Brontë’s language is rich in artistic devices. By analyzing the language of the characters through metaphor, parallelism, and dialogue, students develop stylistic sensitivity.

Example: *“Do you think I am an automaton? — a machine without feelings?”*

Here, Jane’s inner dissatisfaction is expressed through a powerful stylistic device, using rhetorical questions and metaphorical expressions.

Speech acts in the work, in particular, requests, denials, desires and statements expressing emotions, form pragmatic competence in students. For example, they help to distinguish between formal and informal forms of address according to social status.

The following approaches can be effectively used in the lesson using the work “Jane Eyre”:

Contextual analysis - analysis of sentences and phrases according to the development of the plot;

Analysis of figurative language - comparing the speech style of the characters;

Identification of stylistic devices - interpretation of metaphors, epithets, litotes, etc;

Revealing the grammatical structure - studying tenses, modal verbs, inversions;

Comparative analysis - comparing expressions in the work with modern English;

These methods make language lessons not only informative, but also analytical and interactive.

Language is a reflection of culture. Through the work, students will get acquainted not only with the language, but also with the social life of 19th-

century English society, gender roles, moral values, social inequality and human rights. This plays an important role in the formation of intercultural competence.

Conclusion: The use of literary works, especially classical texts, in the process of teaching a foreign language serves as an important tool in ensuring the harmony of language and culture, developing language sensitivity, and forming communication competencies. Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" is a work worthy of effective analysis in foreign language lessons with its artistic and linguistic richness, figurative language, and cultural context.

This article examines various areas of linguistic analysis of the work - lexical, grammatical, stylistic, and pragmatic analysis methods. Through these approaches, students develop not only grammatical knowledge, but also contextual understanding, cultural thinking, and analytical thinking skills.

Linguistic analysis conducted on the example of the work "Jane Eyre" is an effective direction for introducing innovative and in-depth teaching methods in teaching a foreign language, which serves to develop not only language knowledge, but also literary and aesthetic taste and cultural awareness in students. Therefore, the methodology of teaching literary texts based on linguistic analysis in foreign language classes should be more widely introduced and developed.

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